

Influence of spatial region selection on infection sensitivity prediction of tomato calyx using hyperspectral imaging

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Abstract: A fungal infection of tomato calyx is detrimental to its shelf life. Early prediction of shelf life using a non-invasive method enables producers and distributors to manage the logistics efficiently and reduce both food and financial loss. In this paper, near-infrared (NIR) hyperspectral imaging (1000-1700 nm) is used with an XGBoost classifier on a dataset of 93 tomato images acquired one day post harvest to predict if the individual tomato sepals will become infected. The methodology is based on classification of the mean and the variance of spectral signatures from the sepal tip regions, and the focus of this work is to examine the impact of different morphological definitions of 'sepal tip region' on the classifier performance. 90 different selections of sepal pixels are compared, defined using distances from the sepal tip and edges as well as the number of pixels. Our findings suggest that the choice of method for sepal tip extraction influences the final outcome. However, it's important to note that the effectiveness of the method is heavily reliant on the specific dataset and its characteristics. Thus, it's challenging to definitively determine the optimal method applicable on a broader scale. Peak classification performance is F1 (macro average) of 63.6%.

Keywords: Hyperspectral image, Infection prediction, Machine learning, Tomato calyx

1. Motivation

Tomato has a high nutrient and moisture content, which makes it highly susceptible to fungal infections [1]. This leads to a significant loss of quality and value of the produce, and it is a large contributor to food waste [2]. Early prediction of infection sensitivity can be a valuable input for the picking order and logistics management, allowing the more sensitive batches to be transported closer and consumed before the infection takes place [2]. Infection first becomes visible on the tomato calyx (crown, sepals), however, methods to detect, analyze and control this phenomenon are largely unexplored [3]. Hyperspectral imaging is a promising solution because it is shown to be a rapid and noninvasive method to detect fungal infection in various plants, even before it becomes visible to the naked eye [2]. The problem arises from the fact that the sepal tip edges are the first regions to become infected, and these regions are the hardest to analyze with a high level of confidence considering the limited spatial resolution of hyperspectral imaging. This problem prompts the need for the identification of the most critical region for infection discrimination with regard to the sepal morphology.

2. Research questions

The end goal of this paper is to explore if there is a sepal region that ensures the best likelihood for the correct sensitivity prediction. This problem is formulated as binary classification of individual tomato sepals into infected and non-infected classes, using hyperspectral images obtained just one day post harvest. A similar problem is explored in [4] where Random Forest (RF) is used to classify sepals based on the degree of infection, and in [1], where RF and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) regression is used to predict the degree of infection sensitivity, with a special focus on the estimation of the contribution of individual wavelength bands. Besides these, there is little research in the literature closely related to this topic. In both of these works, the whole sepal is used to obtain the average spectral signature. Considering that sepal tips and edges lose moisture the quickest making them more susceptible to infection than the rest of the sepal [1], the question arises if a different approach to the selection of spectral pixels, more

focused on sepal tips and edges, can provide an improvement of the results. An additional level of complexity is introduced by the limited spatial resolution of spectral cameras, resulting in mixing of spectral signatures of the sepal edges with the background. The exploration of this topic questions the traditional approaches in hyperspectral image analysis in the plant imaging field, and sheds light on factors that may be crucial to consider in segmentation or annotation tasks in similar applications.

3. Methodology

Classification is done on a dataset of 93 tomato images [3], with 144 infected and 325 non-infected sepals in total. Images are obtained one day post harvest using Specim FX17 hyperspectral camera, in the NIR range from 1000 to 1700 nm. Assessment if the sepal is infected is done by a team of experts 7 days post harvest. Samples have shown a very low degree of infection, visible only on the sepal tips even on the seventh day, making this problem very complex and emphasizing the need for careful region selection. Classification is done on the basis of individual sepals, however the split into training and test sets is done on the level of whole tomato images to prevent any form of data leakage. The split is done in a stratified manner, with 20% of the sepals saved for the final evaluation. Preprocessing pipeline includes black-white correction and standard normal variate (SNV) correction, standard steps in hyperspectral image processing. Elimination of noisy spectral bands is done, decreasing the number of used spectral channels from 224 to 204. The calyx region is separated from the background using a clusterization procedure. Thanks to the star-like shape of the calyx, sepal tips are located as vertices of its convex hull. Calyx edges and sepal tips are used to define Euclidean distance maps [5] that are later used to sort the sepal pixels and select the ones of interest. Three parameters are used to control the shape of the regions. The first and the most complex parameter is the weighing factor α used to create a combined distance map of the edge and the tip distance maps, using the formula $(\alpha \cdot EDM_{edge} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot EDM_{tip})$. The range of used values is [0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8], where 0 corresponds to using only the tip distance map. To prevent mixing with the background, the boundary of the calyx region is eliminated and the distance map calculation is repeated with the new, reduced calyx region. Three cases of boundary elimination are used: none, one and two rows of pixels removed. Accordingly, the second parameter is defined as the distance from the calyx edge that is eliminated: 0, 1 or 2 rows of pixels. The third parameter is the number of pixels used to calculate the mean spectral signature after all of the sepal pixels are sorted by distance given by the selected distance map. Used values are [5, 15, 25, 35, 45, 55]. The whole process of region definition is illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Using the extracted pixels, the mean signatures and variances are calculated and used as features for the XGBoost [6] classifier training. A grid search was used to obtain the optimal hyperparameters. For each of the region parameter combinations, the top 10 grid search modes are evaluated on the test set (instead of only the best one) to improve the statistical robustness of the analysis. The mean F1 score for the two classes (macro average F1) is used as the final evaluation metric.

4. Solution/Discussion

The best achieved result is an F1 score of 63.6%, indicating that there is room for improvement in making this prediction procedure suitable for the practical application in the industry. It should be

noted that the infection rate is significantly low even after 7 days (e.g. compared to [1]), which highlights challenges faced by noninvasive methods such as the proposed method. Heatmaps of the mean F1 metric for the 10 best classifiers for each of the 30 region parameter combinations are given in Figure 3. Patterns can be observed in these matrices, with the most prominent one being the drop of performance towards the higher number of pixels and higher weight of edge distance maps. The experiment is repeated with different splits of the data with noticeable patterns emerging in each individual split, but never being consistent between multiple splits. These results indicate that there is an impact of region selection on classification performance and that a smaller number of pixels on selected positions may improve the results compared to using the full sepal region. However, in this experiment there is no clear indication on features that enable localization of that optimal region in the general case. This may be attributed to multiple factors related to the dataset, the small size or the low infection rate. On the other hand, this approach processes morphological information (distance maps) and spectral information (mean signature) in two separate steps, which certainly limits the ability to distill and utilize the most discriminant information in a globally optimal way. In conclusion, the search for the optimal region is worth pursuing since it may provide better understanding of the topic and the prediction performance, however it should be done with a larger dataset with a higher infection rate, and using a method that is based on the analysis of spatial and spectral data simultaneously.

Figure 1. Image processing pipeline, from left to right: Input image, content clusters, calyx mask with convex hull and sepal tips, EDM from sepal tips, EDM from the calyx edge, combined EDM with $\alpha=0.7$

Figure 2. Different definitions of sepal tip regions: α on horizontal axis, eliminated border distance on vertical axis and number of pixels illustrated with color gradient.

Figure 3. Heatmaps of mean F1 metric for 10 best classifiers for each of the 30 region parameter combinations

4. References

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